

Briefing Paper: Mapping the training provision of the ESRC Data Resource Training Network services to the UKDS Data Skills Framework

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Background

The UK Data Service (UKDS) launched the [UKDS Data Skills Framework](#) in April 2024. This has received a lot of interest within the social science data skills training ecosystem and among leading statistical organisations (national and international). The Framework was also identified by the ESRC Data Resource Training Network (DRTN) as a useful tool for mapping out the training offering of each service to identify data skills training gaps, overlaps and areas for collaboration.

Methods

During Autumn 2024-Spring 2025, each of the DRTN services completed an exercise to map their training offering against each of the 147 skills within the Framework (see [Appendix](#)). Ten ESRC-funded services completed this exercise: UK Data Service, Admin Data Research UK, Consumer Data Research Centre, CLOSER, Understanding Society, European Social Survey, Scottish Longitudinal Study (Census), ONS Census Longitudinal Study, National Centre for Research Methods, and the Centre for Longitudinal Studies.

The Google Sheet collected the following information from each service for each skill:

Question	Response category
Is this topic within the remit/scope of the training from my 'service'	Yes/No/Don't know
Does my service have training on this?	Yes/No/Being Planned
If yes, what format is it in?	Event/Online Material/Both/Other
Additional comments if needed	Open field

Key results

Gaps and overlaps

The essential data skills for quantitative analysis outlined in the Framework are very well covered by the DRTN services. There are very few gaps in training provision - with only 4 of the 147 data skills in the Framework not covered by existing training (see Table 1). In total, training exists from at least one of the DRTN services for 143/147 skills. Of these, 47 skills are covered by 1-2 of the DRTN services. The remaining skills (n=96) are covered by at least 3 DRTN services (see Appendix). Note, there are no skills that are covered by all ten services.

Table 1: The four skills not covered by existing DRTN training provision.

Skill number	Skill name
4.12	Interoperability in archival management
7.07	Journal and publication requirements for reproducibility
11.09	The English Longitudinal Study of Ageing
11.11	The Housing Surveys

Discussion

Overview

The mapping has been a useful exercise, and the results can be used for planning and sharing practice among DRTN services. The results are also useful for learners – ideally this would sit as a top-level/central resource for learners (in a different format) and would link out to all relevant training from DRTN members. This would drive traffic to the training and give learners a more holistic view of their data skills training needs. The exercise will, therefore, be of use to the new ESRC-funded Skills Leadership Hub to show the remit of each service training provider, what we currently do and current collaborations. It has potential to be developed into a dynamic resource for learners.

Quantity within the mapping exercise does not reflect quality/depth of training. For example, Skill 10.10 The Crime Surveys is covered by one service only (UK Data Service). However, it is covered extensively - with a 2.5-hour asynchronous data skills module Exploring crime surveys with R , an annual Crime Survey User Conference, regular live drop-in sessions for survey users and a Data skills module: Introduction to survey data, covering weighting and many other subjects relevant to getting started with survey data. There are many examples of this from all the training providers. Similarly, the mapping exercise does not try to show the detail of a services' training on a particular skill. This is very important when looking at the mapping results i.e. there may be eight services that have been identified as providers of training in a skill, but that training may be very limited within a service e.g. one slide (see limitations section for more information).

Each DRTN service has a clear remit, and training is focussed distinctly on a data 'type' and/or topics that a service is funded to provide training on. Although there is some overlap in the topics of the data skills training, this is not a bad thing per se: variety matters in terms of styles, providers, formats, detail and dates. There is huge demand for data skills training with courses selling out and asynchronous materials widely used despite some repetition of topics between the services.

Next steps for the DRTN

Step 1: Explore the training available for the four skills not covered by any of the DRTN members.

- Skill 11:11: Provide training on the Housing Surveys. DRTN to organise a collaborative webinar on Housing Surveys (to include cross-sectional, longitudinal and Census data). UK Data Service to produce a data skills module on Housing Surveys.
- Skill 11:09: Explore training on the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing. Explore the training that exists currently outside of the services that completed this mapping exercise (primarily the ELSA team). Include a presentation from the ELSA team in the collaborative DRTN webinar on Ageing, scheduled for 2025. Explore the potential for a collaborative Data Skills Modules on ELSA and potentially expand this internationally to include global ageing datasets.
- Skill 7:07: DRTN to produce a slide on 'Journal and publication requirements for reproducibility' for use by DRTN members in training on the wider theme of reproducibility.
- Skill 4:12: Interoperability in archival management – this falls within the remit of CLOSER, ADRUK, UKDS and CDRC. Arrange internal training for DRTN members on this topic.

Step 2: Identify a skill that is provided by several DRTN services. Use this as a pilot to form a short-life network around this skill. A network could include activities such as:

- Identifying the extent and detail of the training on this skill from each service.
- Sharing materials, practice and learning objectives.
- Re-using materials from others.
- Creating core materials.
- Signposting to other materials.
- Creating a simple joint resource e.g. a combined slide set, jointly badged.
- Collaborating to create a more complex resource such as a 'pathway' on a skill.

Limitations

This is a snapshot of the training at one point in time. Training provision from each service will change, grow and evolve. The mapping exercise could be done on annual basis by DRTN but ideally it would be captured more dynamically, in real-time.

There is some inconsistency in data collection. Services may have interpreted the skills in different ways. For example, one service commented that they did not give training on several skills directly (e.g. how to access data, how to use STATA, how to design a research question) but these topics are embedded within the training that they provide. Some services

noted that, for some skills, they only had a small amount of content, so they were unsure if to include it – some did include it and some did not.

There may be legacy training resources from previous DRTN members/data services that are not included in this mapping exercise (for example Urban Big Data Centre or Business and Local Government Data Research Centre).

Conclusions

This mapping exercise has provided a valuable overview of the current data skills training landscape across the DRTN services in relation to the UKDS Data Skills Framework. It confirms that the essential quantitative data skills in the Framework are broadly well covered by DRTN services, with only a small number of gaps identified. The findings highlight opportunities for future collaboration, particularly in addressing the four uncovered skills and exploring shared training in widely offered areas. Importantly, the exercise also underlines the need for more nuanced understanding of training quality and depth, beyond simple coverage. The results will serve as a practical resource for both training providers and learners, and have clear potential to evolve into a dynamic, centralised tool to guide data skills development. Moving forward, the DRTN is well positioned to build on this work by coordinating targeted training development, fostering resource sharing, and enhancing the overall coherence of data skills provision across the UK social science research community.

Authors and acknowledgements

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Admin Data Research UK

Consumer Data Research Centre

CLOSER

European Social Survey

National Centre for Research Methods, and the Centre for Longitudinal Studies

ONS Census Longitudinal Study

Scottish Longitudinal Study (Census)

UK Data Service

Understanding Society

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